

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL BASIS FOR STUDYING MEDIA LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *In this article, media language is considered as an autonomous object of science in an interdisciplinary and philosophical and scientific context, in which the scientific and theoretical views of world media linguists on the non-linearity, versatility and multifunctionality of the language are revealed, and complex aspects of its phenomenal essence that go beyond the simplified structural and functional approach.*

Keywords: *media language, mediacommunication, media discourse, mediallynguistics, mediatexts.*

The problem of "language and media" is not limited to the current information boom that is entering our lives. The study of the language of media as a cultural tool, social interaction and a conceptual model of social reality in the minds of a wide audience has a long history and has not lost its relevance today. There is a large corpus of scientific papers devoted to the study of language features in the media.

The language used today in the media environment has its own characteristics, which can be seen in its wide use in various projects and ideas at the global, national-cultural, regional and personal levels. In the language of the media, this is important for the intellectual, ideological, emotional, moral, methodological and aesthetic characteristics of the audience, as well as its responsiveness to news requirements and goals. It also needs to consider how the audience wants information to be presented, messages to be delivered and received.

In fact, the concept of media language and its importance for modern society is a very broad and multifaceted topic, which is determined by the multifacetedness of mass media in general, and media language in particular. Russian linguist E.P.Zinoveva's following opinion confirms that "mass media actively shape the linguistic landscape of the world as part of cultural and social practice" [3].

Modern mass media language and its texts have become the object of research in mediallynguistics. According to T.G.Dobrosklonskaya, mediallynguistics is a science that studies the use of language in the field of mass communication. In a broader context, mass communication refers to the institutional development and dissemination of symbolic materials through the transmission and storage of information [1]. In fact, under this new direction in linguistics, various fields studying media texts come together, and all of them help to express the dialectical integrity of linguistic and media properties.

D.M.Teshabaeva considers media communication as a sphere that maximizes its potential as a functional integrity, and the issues of forming the views, values and culture of information consumers are to find ways to organize the information world in the minds of readers, viewers and listeners, to handle information, emphasizes that this requires development and formation of a system of new methods and skills [8].

Mediallynguistics studies the entire multilevel structure of media texts, including the influence of the methods of creation and distribution on linguistic-format features, functional-

genre classification, phonological, syntagmatic and stylistic characteristics, interpretive features, cultural-specific features, ideological modality and pragmalinguistic value.

A.K.Khamidova in her article "Medialinguistics - a new paradigm in the study of media language" considers medialinguistics as a new field of linguistic research that studies the language and other aspects of texts created and distributed by the media. The article deals with the main problems associated with media linguistics, including the influence of the ways of creating and distributing media texts on their linguistic and format features, functional-genre classification, phonological, syntagmatic and stylistic features, interpretation features, cultural-specific features, ideological modality, pragmalinguistic value, etc. The author also studies the social significance of media linguistics and its impact on the use of language in the modern information society [9].

According to the article by T.V.Shmeleva and A.A.Veselova "Media language: visual component", media texts include various visual elements used to convey information and create an emotional atmosphere. The visual component of the media language includes the use of color, shape, composition, font, images and other elements to create a certain effect on the audience. One of the main tasks of media language is to manage the perception of the audience and form its opinion. For example, the choice of certain colors and fonts can be used to enhance the emotional impact on the audience, and the composition of images and text can be used to create a certain context and convey certain information [11].

In addition, the language of the media can be used to create social reality and form public relations. For example, images and text used in news programs and promotional materials can influence public opinion and audience behavior. Thus, the language of the media on the basis of this publication can be defined as a language in which visual elements are used to convey information, create an emotional environment, control audience perception and form social reality [11].

It should be noted that the media language is not a single and standardized language, but a set of tools and methods that can be used differently in different media texts in accordance with the goals and objectives of the creator. In the article by V.Yu.Kozhanova "The Receptive Aspect of Creating a Media Text", the language of media is interpreted as a system of signs and symbols used in media texts to convey information and create a certain emotional atmosphere. The language of the media is defined in terms of the impact of the media text on the perception of the recipients.

In the article by M.N.Cherkasova "Media event and media symbol as an example of hate speech from the point of view of media linguistics and media criticism", media language is defined as a special type of language that is used to create certain symbols and events in the media environment and influences the formation of public opinion and feelings. The author of the article explores media language from the point of view of its role in the formation of hate speech, which is becoming more and more common in the media environment. In this context, media language is considered as a means of creating media images and media events that create a certain emotional atmosphere and mood in the audience. [10]. M.N.Cherkasova draws attention to the fact that hate speech created with the help of media language can have a negative impact on public opinion and lead to social conflicts. At the same time, the importance of media-linguistic and media-critical analysis of hate speech and media events is emphasized, which contributes to the prevention and reduction of their negative consequences.

A.V.Polonsky, V.G.Glushkova, M.A.Ryapolova believe that "the peculiarity of the language of the media is that it is focused on the current context of life and the target audience, is

a quick recording, explanation and interpretation of rapidly changing contexts life in the right modality, that it has the ability to provide the necessary level of information and spiritual interaction of subjects and form a common picture of the world for all people" [7].

A.V.Mikhaleva defines media language as a type of professional discourse used in mass communication, that is, in print publications, television, radio and the Internet. It is a specific language used to create and transmit information in mass communication [6].

It should be noted that the definition of media language depends on the aspect and direction of its study. In each field of research, media language is analyzed from different perspectives. For example, within the framework of the functional-pragmatic approach, media discourse and media language are seen as a means of performing communicative tasks related to information transfer and influencing the audience. Within the cognitive approach, media discourse and media language are analyzed in terms of cognitive processes based on understanding and interpreting information in mass communication.

N.I.Klushina studies the methodological side of the language of media and offers an intentional approach to the description of media styles. Here the author's intention serves as the basis for determining the methodology of various media texts and types of communication. This method allows you to describe the creative ideas of the author, identify ideological concepts and describe both the sender and the recipient from a cognitive point of view. This approach considers the creator of the discourse and the recipient, or media discourse, and identifies three types of media discourse in the media space: when the recipient has no expression, information-oriented news or news discourse, templates, many citations and recommendations; journalistic or fashionable discourse aimed at persuasion and using linguistic means, requiring authorial authority; tabloid entertainment discourse with sensational headlines, controversy and information [4].

This typology distinguishes media discourse from advertising produced for purely economic purposes outside the media space. Media styles are considered as a link between different texts in the media, ensuring the coherence and consistency of different texts. Media styles are specific features of texts that ensure the harmony of media discourse, allowing you to combine different texts into a common system of media texts.

From a methodological point of view, media language is a specific type of linguistic activity associated with the use of language in the media space. This type of linguistic activity is characterized by specific features of the use of language in media texts, including in public speech, television and radio programs, journalism, advertising, PR, etc. Media studies study the linguistic features of media texts, including vocabulary, grammar, methodology, rhetoric and much more. The sociocultural, political and economic aspects of language activity in the media space are also studied [5].

In recent years, with the help of new epistemological methods generally accepted in science, media language is seen as an autonomous object of science in an interdisciplinary and philosophical-scientific context, in which nonlinearity, multifaceted and multifunctionality of language, as well as complex aspects of its phenomenal essence that go beyond a simplified structural-functional approach is taken into account.

A critical approach to media and an understanding of media language can help people become more informed and critical thinking members of society. After all, media language has a significant impact on our thinking and behavior. With the help of media language, stereotypes are

created, opinions are formed and the minds of the audience are manipulated. Media language can create emotional attachments to certain brands or ideas, as well as influence our attitudes toward various social and political issues.

Since the beginning of the second half of the 20th century, the media began to rapidly develop and increase in size. The press, radio and television became more popular, new technologies and the Internet led to the formation of a global news space. These processes are so important for society that the modern world is characterized by the comprehensive impact of information and telecommunication technologies on social life. The concept of information society was proposed. Mass communication has become one of the most active areas of language use. A large amount of texts are distributed every day through mass media, which leads to an increase in interest in this field of research in academic science [2]. Therefore, in our opinion, it is one of today's urgent issues to include mediallynguistics as a compulsory subject in the curricula of all secondary schools and higher education institutions along with media literacy.

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